

Supplementary Methods and Results

Inter-sexual phenotypic divergence is correlated with habitat structure in an invasive lizard

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	Timing					Frequency	Location
	2021	2021	2021	2022	2023		
	May	July	Sept.	May	March		
Anole sampling	o	o	o	o	o	As possible	Transects
Vegetation diameter	o	o	o			Once overall	At ends of each transect
Vegetation height				o		Once overall	At ends of each transect
Vegetation cover	o	o	o			Once per sampling period	At ends of each transect
Arthropod abundance	o	o	o			Once per sampling period	Transects
Anole abundance	o	o	o			Once per sampling period	Transects
GIS						Once overall	By Island

Fig. S1. Sampling schema for the study indicating timing, location and frequency of sampling for each dataset and representative location and size of sample areas for vegetation measures (each performed at both ends of each transect).

Fig. S2. Measures quantified for anole morphological characteristics and body size.

Fig. S3. STRUCTURE plot of individual population assignment for $K = 2$ (inferred optimal K), indicating lack of variation among islands in population assignments.

Fig. S4. Variation in environmental characteristics among sites. Boxes indicate the interquartile range, with whiskers indicating minimum and maximum values, and the bar indicating the median. Orange = Anijima, Green = Chichijima, Purple = Hahajima.

Table S1. Sampling information by site and date (number of males/females).

Site	Anijima		Chichijima				Hahajima			
	1	2	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
May 2021	0/0	0/0	1/0	4/0	3/0	5/0	4/0	0/0	2/0	2/0
Jul 2021	0/0	0/0	1/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/3	0/0	1/0	1/1
Sep 2021	8/0	4/3	3/0	3/1	2/3	2/1	4/1	1/1	1/1	2/1
May 2022	10/5	10/1	5/6	5/5	5/5	5/4	7/3	3/2	5/4	5/5
Mar 2023	3/0	1/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	0/0	1/0	2/0	1/0
Total	36/9		44/25				42/22			

Table S2. Coefficients of variation for each of the morphological measurements over 10 repeated measures of the same individual.

Measure	COV
SVL	0.71
FL-L	1.64
FL-R	2.24
TIB-L	0.76
TIB-R	1.50
FTL-L	1.34
FTL-R	1.40
FAL-L	4.92
FAL-R	3.17
HUM-L	3.56
HUM-R	2.07
HL	0.73
HW	0.63
HH	2.50
MO	2.45

Table S3. Results of GLM post-hoc contrasts for vegetation height and diameter.

Shown are overall effects. Test statistics overall are Chisq values from anova run on GLM results, and pairwise contrasts are from Tukey contrasts implemented with the glht function of the multcomp package in R [1].

Factor/contrast	Vegetation height		Vegetation diameter	
	Test stat	P value	Test stat	P value
Overall	532.8	<0.001	95.5	<0.001
Anijima-Chichijima	17.44	<0.001	6.75	<0.001
Anijima-Hahajima	22.90	<0.001	9.62	<0.001
Hahajima-Chichijima	6.68	<0.001	3.29	0.003

Table S4. Comparison of insect resource and anole abundance and diversity metrics among islands. Overall results are for Kruskal-Wallis tests, inter-island pairwise contrasts are Dunn post-hoc tests. Ani = Anijima, Chichi = Chichijima, Haha = Hahajima. Test statistics are chi-square values for overall Kruskal-Wallis tests and z statistics for post-hoc Dunn tests.

Character	Factor/contrast	test stat	P value
Arthropod richness	Overall	12.720	<0.001
	Ani-Chichi	-2.449	0.007
	Ani-Haha	-3.470	<0.001
	Haha-Chichi	-1.021	0.154
Arthropod diversity	Overall	7.578	0.020
	Ani-Chichi	-0.949	0.171
	Ani-Haha	-2,712	0.003
	Haha-Chichi	-1.763	0.039
Arthropod abundance	Overall	12.993	<0.001
	Ani-Chichi	-3.517	<0.001
	Ani-Haha	-2.442	0.007
	Haha-Chichi	1.076	0.141
Anole abundance	Overall	23.663	<0.001
	Ani-Chichi	-4.780	<0.001
	Ani-Haha	-1.606	0.054
	Haha-Chichi	3.173	<0.001

Table S5. Results of lmer analyses of morphological traits with SVL and island as factors, the interaction between these factors, and site as a random factor. Ani = Anijima, Chichi = Chichijima, Haha = Hahajima. Test statistics are Chi-square for main model and z values for post-hoc contrasts using glht (on an additive model without the interaction effect). Results for an analysis of the sub-sampled dataset of males with equal sample size to the female dataset is provided in the right-hand columns.

Character	Factor/contrast	Males		Females		Males (equal)	
		test stat	P value	test stat	P value	test stat	P value
Hind limb	SVL	116.4	<0.001	44.6	<0.001	65.7	<0.001
	Island	20.3	<0.001	1.5	0.468	11.3	0.004
	interaction	2.9	0.240	2.8	0.252	1.9	0.384
	Ani-Chichi	2.74	0.017	-	-	0.6	0.842
	Ani-Haha	4.64	< 0.001	-	-	2.5	0.031
	Haha-Chichi	2.11	0.089	-	-	2.5	0.031
Fore limb	SVL	165.2	<0.001	53.4	<0.001	81.3	<0.001
	Island	38.3	<0.001	0.4	0.825	20.9	<0.001
	interaction	1.4	0.491	0.1	0.962	5.2	0.076
	Ani-Chichi	4.01	< 0.001	-	-	2.3	0.056
	Ani-Haha	6.12	< 0.001	-	-	4.3	<0.001
	Haha-Chichi	2.28	0.058	-	-	2.7	0.019
HW	SVL	108.0	<0.001	37.1	<0.001	47.3	<0.001
	Island	0.9	0.642	1.1	0.579	1.2	0.563
	interaction	3.3	0.193	1.6	0.440	3.7	0.157
	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
HL	SVL	231.9	<0.001	68.5	<0.001	90.2	<0.001
	Island	8.9	0.012	1.0	0.619	6.8	0.034
	interaction	3.0	0.221	0.4	0.838	2.4	0.300
	Ani-Chichi	0.207	0.977	-	-	-0.02	0.999
	Ani-Haha	2.655	0.022	-	-	1.8	0.158
	Haha-Chichi	2.522	0.031	-	-	2.4	0.041
MO	SVL	191.9	<0.001	39.1	<0.001	87.2	<0.001
	Island	4.7	0.095	0.7	0.710	1.4	0.489
	interaction	6.2	0.045	0.5	0.790	3.8	0.153
	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
HH	SVL	48.7	<0.001	10.6	<0.001	22.7	<0.001
	Island	4.1	0.128	2.0	0.710	0.95	0.621
	interaction	4.3	0.118	0.4	0.815	1.6	0.439

	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-	-	-
FFA	SVL	86.0	<0.001	37.0	<0.001	46.6	<0.001
	Island	9.3	0.010	0.4	0.829	8.9	0.012
	interaction	0.8	0.674	0.4	0.825	0.08	0.961
	Ani-Chichi	-0.351	0.934	-	-	0.4	0.906
	Ani-Haha	2.418	0.041	-	-	2.4	0.039
	Haha-Chichi	2.833	0.013	-	-	2.6	0.022
HFA	SVL	73.4	<0.001	41.7	<0.001	43.0	<0.001
	Island	9.2	0.010	1.904	0.386	2.1	0.358
	interaction	0.5	0.788	0.015	0.993	6.0	0.049
	Ani-Chichi	2.668	0.021	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	2.451	0.038	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-0.133	0.990	-	-	-	-

Table S6. Contrasts of residuals among islands. Overall results are for Kruskal-Wallace tests, inter-island pairwise contrasts are Dunn post-hoc tests. Ani = Anijima, Chichi = Chichijima, Haha = Hahajima. Test statistics are chi-square values for overall Kruskal-Wallace tests and z statistics for post-hoc Dunn tests.

Character	Factor/contrast	males		females	
		test stat	P value	test stat	P value
Hindlimb	Overall	29.531	<0.001	0.637	0.73
	Ani-Chichi	-3.680	0.0002	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-5.357	<0.001	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-1.806	0.0354	-	-
Forelimb	Overall	25.475	<0.001	1.387	0.5
	Ani-Chichi	-2.827	0.0035	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-5.046	<0.001	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	2.368	0.0089	-	-
HW	Overall	0.506	0.78	1.290	0.52
	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-
HL	Overall	7.144	0.03	1.568	0.46
	Ani-Chichi	-0.011	0.495	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-2.249	0.0184	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-2.356	0.0278	-	-
MO	Overall	3.832	0.15	1.553	0.46
	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-
HH	Overall	2.90	0.23	5.238	0.07
	Ani-Chichi	-	-	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-	-	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-	-	-	-
HFA	Overall	7.840	0.02	2.001	0.86
	Ani-Chichi	-2.644	0.0123	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-2.212	0.0202	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	0.426	0.335	-	-
FFA	Overall	7.582	0.02	0.313	0.86
	Ani-Chichi	0.019	0.493	-	-
	Ani-Haha	-2.300	0.0161	-	-
	Haha-Chichi	-2.441	0.0220	-	-

Table S7. Results of Imer analysis of the relationship between site-level factors (vegetation height, log vegetation diameter and anole abundance) and mean forelimb and hindlimb length at each site for each sex.

		Hindlimb		Forelimb	
		Chi	p	Chi	p
All data	Sex	0.055	0.304	0.914	0.339
	Vegetation height	1.029	0.310	3.340	0.068
	Vegetation diameter	14.81	<0.001	3.160	0.075
	Anole abundance	4.025	0.045	1.560	0.211
	Veg height:sex	19.061	<0.001	6.463	0.011
	Veg diam:sex	2.040	0.602	0.028	0.867
	Anole ab:sex	0.272	0.015	0.002	0.967
Equal	Sex	0.985	0.344	0.299	0.585
sample-size data	Vegetation height	4.024	0.045	5.970	0.015
	Vegetation diameter	5.626	0.018	0.259	0.611
	Anole abundance	2.314	0.369	2.314	0.128
	Veg height:sex	11.936	<0.001	9.231	0.002
	Veg diam:sex	2.269	0.132	1.233	0.267
	Anole ab:sex	0.327	0.567	0.266	0.606

Table S8. Population genetic metrics based on 1807 genome-wide SNPs and 20 males lizards per island. Observed homozygosity (Ho), expected heterozygosity (He), allelic richness (Ar), number of alleles (alleles) and number of private alleles (private) are shown.

Population genetic metrics	Ho	He	Ar	Alleles	Private
Anijima	0.119	0.112	1.344	2987	444
Chichijima	0.113	0.114	1.296	2952	397
Hahajima	0.116	0.115	1.360	2971	376

Table S9. Results of AMOVA analysis for genetic variation among islands. The percentage variation at each hierarchical level and p-value in each case is shown.

AMOVA	% variation	P value
Within samples	49.34	0.01
Between samples within populations	50.46	0.01
Between populations	0.20	0.44

References

1. Hothorn T., Bretz F., Westfall P. 2008 Simultaneous inference in general parametric models. *Biom J* **50**, 346-363.